

Review Article

Recent Advances in the Prevention and Treatment of Chemotherapy-induced Cardiotoxicity

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ABSTRACT

The current study aimed to overview recent advances in preventing and treating chemotherapy-induced cardiotoxicity. Chemotherapy is widely used in cancer treatment, however, it can have adverse effects on the heart, leading to the development of risk factors, such as hypertension, obesity, dyslipidemia, and metabolic syndrome. Anthracycline compounds are the most commonly used chemotherapy agents and are associated with an increased risk of developing anthracycline-induced cardiotoxicity (AIC). The precise mechanisms underlying AIC remain a subject of debate, but evidence suggests that the primary causes are the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and subsequent oxidative stress. Several risk factors have been linked to the development of AIC, including cumulative dose, pre-existing cardiac disease, age, gender, and cardiac risk factors. Genetic susceptibility may also play a role as a potential risk factor for AIC. In order to protect cardiac function, various strategies have been explored, such as developing less-toxic derivatives of anthracyclines, determining safer cumulative anthracycline doses, and identifying new cardioprotective agents. Prophylactic treatment with cardioprotective agents is the best approach for high-risk patients. This article reviewed the present strategies for protecting cancer patients from AIC based on effective cardioprotective drugs along with the balance between their benefits and potential adverse effects.

1. Introduction

The considerable advances in detecting and treating cancer patients have led to a remarkable increase in life expectancy during the past two decades. Chemotherapy, with anti-cancer effects in the treatment of both solid and hematologic malignancies, significantly contributes to the potential for cancer cure and subsequent improved survival rates. Nevertheless, these therapies are not without their drawbacks, particularly with regard to their impact on cardiac health. Adverse effects on the heart encompass a spectrum of consequences, including the development of multiple risk factors, such as hypertension, obesity, dyslipidemia, and metabolic syndrome. Additionally, there is an increased likelihood of subsequent cardiotoxicity, which may accelerate cardiomyopathy in patients treated with antitumor agents^{1,2}.

Anthracycline compounds, including daunorubicin, doxorubicin, epirubicin, idarubicin, and mitoxantrone, are

the most common chemotherapy agents. These compounds used extensively to remedy different kinds of cancer, such as breast cancer, lymphoma, esophageal carcinoma, sarcoma, small cell carcinoma of the lung, pediatric leukemia, solid tumors³. However, caution is required for the clinical usefulness of anthracyclines due to their various adverse effects, especially the development of anthracycline-induced cardiotoxicity (AIC) that increases the risk of developing cardiac dysfunction and impacts the quality of life and mortality of cancer patients. It is estimated that regimens using anthracyclines would increase the risk of developing late-onset heart failure in 5 to 23 percent of patients. Furthermore, this cardiac complication amplifies mortality rates by 5 times. However, the prognosis can be significantly enhanced through early detection and preventive measures^{4,5}.

Anthracycline-induced cardiotoxicity is thought to arise

through a range of mechanisms. These include the inhibition of essential cellular processes such as DNA, RNA, and protein synthesis, as well as interference with DNA repair, replication, and transcription. Additionally, anthracyclines have been shown to generate reactive oxygen species (ROS), which can lead to oxidative stress within cardiac cells. Another proposed mechanism involves the inhibition of topoisomerase II, leading to the initiation of apoptosis. Furthermore, anthracyclines can interfere with DNA strand separation and impede helicase activity. These multifaceted mechanisms collectively contribute to the development of cardiotoxicity associated with anthracycline use^{6,7}. Most mechanisms involve the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), leading to oxidative stress as the primary cause of anthracycline-induced cardiotoxicity, mediating both death and survival of cardiomyocytes⁸. Recent advances in understanding the pathophysiology of AIC and identification of patient risk factors have led to the exploration of cardio-protective agents and the development of new approaches for the prevention and treatment of patients prone to cardiomyopathy.

Regarding the differences in clinical characteristics and pathophysiology of various types of cancer, and consequently, different responses to anthracycline chemotherapy, it is difficult to define a single strategy to prevent/treat AIC. With this in mind and considering the fact that the AIC may cause irreversible damage to the myocardium, the early detection of cardiotoxicity and developing prevention strategies is a more practical approach than treatment⁹. Extensive efforts have been conducted to monitor, prevent, and treat AIC, ranging from the continuous infusion of anthracycline, use of liposomal drugs or their less cardiotoxic derivative (such as epirubicin or idarubicin), and the concomitant therapy by cardioprotective agents¹⁰. This paper investigated the present strategies for protecting cancer patients from AIC based on effective cardioprotective drugs and the balance between their benefits and harms.

2. Mechanisms of anthracycline-induced cardiotoxicity

The exact molecular mechanism of AIC remains controversial and is likely to be multifactorial. However, a growing body of evidence has indicated that the generation of ROS and subsequent oxidative stress is the primary cause of AIC. The AIC is a cumulative, dose-dependent phenomenon leading to direct oxidative damage to cellular components, including chromatin and DNA. In the heart, this process manifests as typical pathologic changes, such as swelling and disruption of the mitochondria, vacuolar degeneration of the sarcoplasmic reticulum, and myofilament degeneration and subsequent loss of myocyte^{11,12}.

Anthracycline-induced generation of ROS can occur through at least two enzymatic and nonenzymatic pathways in cardiomyocytes, leading to cell death through apoptotic pathways^{13,14}. Anthracyclines would lead to the

reduction of oxygen to form a superoxide anion radical due to interaction with the cardiolipin, a phospholipid located within the inner mitochondrial membrane at the site of the respiratory chain, and other cytochrome-containing enzymes. This situation causes mitochondrial damage, followed by caspase 9 and caspase 3 activation, opening of the mitochondrial permeability transition pore, and the release of cytochrome C into the cytosol and then induction of cell apoptosis¹⁵⁻¹⁷. In contrast to rapidly dividing cancer cells that the anthracycline-induced DNA damage is the primary mechanism responsible for their killing efficacy, the toxicity in cardiomyocytes is related to free radical formation due to their high reliance on oxidative substrate metabolism, which requires more volume of mitochondria, and therefore they are much more sensitive to the anthracycline-induced oxidative stress even in lower anthracycline concentrations¹⁸.

Anthracycline-induced oxidative stress activates several intracellular pathways consisting of stress-activated protein kinases and mitogen-activated protein kinases. These pathways regulate cellular responses to stimuli, either survival or apoptosis. The balance between those cytotoxic or cytoprotective pathways is determinant in the final cardiomyocytes fate and response to anthracyclines^{12,19}. From the molecular point of view, it is also well established that topoisomerase 2 β (Top2 β) is the principal molecular target of anthracycline's antitumor activity, which modulates DNA topology during replication, recombination, and transcription. Anthracycline-mediated inhibition of Top2 β would lead to the accumulation of protein-associated DNA breaks, mitochondrial dysfunction, generation of reactive oxygen species, and induction of apoptosis in treated cells due to irreversible stabilization of the complexes of DNA and Top2 β in the cleaved status²⁰⁻²³. The development of novel treatments decreasing the toxicity of anthracyclines requires substantial attention to these cytoprotective pathways and molecular issues. On the basis of this molecular insight, new strategies have been developed for changes in cancer treatment protocols and exploring the novel cardioprotective agents against anthracycline chemotherapy.

3. Risk Factors for Cardiotoxicity

The AIC is cumulative and *dose-dependent*, which may range from subtle changes in myocardial strain or biomarkers to subclinical decrements of left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) and overt cardiomyopathy²⁴. Anthracycline-related cardiac toxicity has been classified as acute onset (within the first week of treatment), early (occurring < 1 year), or late onset (occurring > 1 year) after anthracycline treatment²⁵. In contrast to acute-onset toxicity, which occurs in less than 1 % of patients and is a dose-independent, delayed AIC manifest in a dose-dependent fashion. It manifests as a progressive endomyocardial damage rather than a pericarditis-myocarditis syndrome. Due to additional cancer treatment or other cardiovascular risk factors, the majority of patients who develop early-onset toxicity indicate late-

onset cardiomyopathy²⁶.

Available studies suggest that various clinical risk factors have been linked to the development of AIC. These factors include age >65 years, pre-existing cardiac disease, female gender, and cardiac risk factors, cumulative dose²⁷. Other conditions like hypertension, hyperlipidemia, concurrent mediastinal radiation, diabetes, and obesity, may also impact cardiotoxicity risk after anthracycline therapy²⁷.

The AIC is unpredictable in individuals, even with similar cumulative doses and clinical conditions¹². This suggests that aside from the risk factors listed above, genetic susceptibility may also be a potential risk factor for anthracycline cardiotoxicity, causing a wide variation in an individual's sensitivity to cardiac toxicity. Potential genetic modulators of this sensitivity as well as genes involved in the anthracycline metabolism pathways, have been implicated in cardiotoxicity development²⁸. In contrast, several gene variants, including variants in ABCB1, ABCB4, ABCC1, and in the solute SLC28A3 or hCNT3 gene, have also conferred significant protection against AIC²⁹. Several studies have recently investigated the prognostic value of genetic variants for early detection of AIC³⁰⁻³². Moreover, a recent systematic review that was published has revealed that genetic variations in genes related to the biochemistry of anthracyclines and the pathways associated with cardiomyopathy could potentially serve as predictors for AIC³³.

4. Strategies for the protection of cardiac function

Besides advances in understanding the exact molecular mechanism underlying AIC, continued efforts have been initiated seeking potential strategies to prevent or treat cardiac complications of cancer chemotherapy. Since anthracyclines improve the life expectancy of patients with cancer, ongoing efforts have been directed toward developing more effective methods for improving early detection of cardiac injury and dysfunction, developing less-toxic derivatives of anthracyclines, determining the safer cumulative anthracycline doses, and finally, identification of new cardioprotective agents as prophylactic treatment. It is of utmost importance to consider opportunities to develop strategies for the primary prevention of cardiotoxicity that protect the heart before it develops clinically evident damage. Despite the lack of universally well-established specific therapies for the prevention or treatment of anthracycline-induced cardiac dysfunction, all proposed preventive approaches during anthracycline treatment are categorized as primary and secondary prevention based on the patient's clinical condition^{1,10}. Primary prevention includes all potential strategies in which anthracycline cardiotoxic potency is reduced due to continuous infusion of anthracycline, use of liposomal forms of drugs, or implementation of less-toxic derivatives (such as epirubicin or idarubicin) as well as prophylactic treatment with cardioprotective agents

(dexrazoxane) in conjunction with cancer therapy³⁴⁻³⁶. Secondary prevention strategies involve the use of sensitive imaging or cardiac biomarkers to early detection and treatment of left ventricular dysfunction before the development of overt cardiac dysfunction and apply to interventions for high-risk patients with subclinical cardiotoxicity³⁷⁻⁴⁰. As long as there is no consensus therapy for AIC, evidence suggests that prophylactic treatment with cardioprotective agents is best for high-risk patients. The following section provides an overview of cardioprotective agents with natural or synthetic origins used in conjunction with cancer therapy before it develops clinically evident damage.

5. Cardioprotective agents

5.1. Dexrazoxane

Dexrazoxane is an iron-chelating agent used as a cardioprotective agent in cancer patients undergoing anthracycline chemotherapy. It works by inhibiting the formation of anthracycline-iron complexes that generate free radicals leading to oxidative stress and subsequent cardiotoxicity⁴¹. Dexrazoxane has been shown to reduce the incidence and severity of AIC without affecting the antitumor efficacy of anthracyclines⁴². A meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials showed that dexrazoxane significantly reduced the risk of developing cardiac dysfunction in patients treated with anthracyclines compared to controls⁴³. The American Society of Clinical Oncology recommends the usage of dexrazoxane for patients receiving a cumulative dose of anthracyclines higher than 250 mg/m²⁴⁴.

5.2. Beta-Blockers

Beta-blockers are a group of medications employed in the treatment of hypertension and other cardiovascular diseases. They work by blocking the effects of adrenaline on the heart, reducing the heart rate and blood pressure. In cancer patients undergoing anthracycline chemotherapy, beta-blockers have been shown to have a protective effect against AIC⁴⁵. They reduce the incidence and severity of left ventricular dysfunction and the risk of heart failure and mortality⁴⁶. A meta-analysis of RCTs showed that beta-blockers significantly reduced the risk of progressing cardiac dysfunction in patients treated with anthracyclines, compared to controls⁴⁷.

5.3. Angiotensin receptor blockers and angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors and

Angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs) and angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (ACEIs) are a class of drugs used to treat hypertension and other cardiovascular diseases. They inhibit the effects of angiotensin II on the heart and blood vessels, leading to a reduction in blood pressure and enhancement of cardiac function. In cancer patients undergoing anthracycline chemotherapy, ACEIs

and ARBs have been shown to have a protective effect against AIC⁴⁸. They reduce the incidence and severity of left ventricular dysfunction and the risk of heart failure and mortality⁴⁹. A meta-analysis of RCTs reported that ACEIs and ARBs significantly decreased the risk of developing cardiac dysfunction in patients treated with anthracyclines compared to controls⁵⁰.

5.4. Statins

Statins are a class of drugs that are employed in the treatment of hyperlipidemia and other cardiovascular diseases. They function by inhibiting the enzyme HMG-CoA reductase, a key enzyme involved in the synthesis of cholesterol synthesis in the liver. In cancer patients undergoing anthracycline chemotherapy, statins have been shown to have a protective effect against AIC⁵¹. They reduce the incidence and severity of left ventricular dysfunction and the risk of heart failure and mortality⁵². A meta-analysis of RCTs reported that statins significantly reduced the risk of developing cardiac dysfunction in patients treated with anthracyclines compared to controls⁵³.

5.5. Omega-3 Fatty Acids

Omega-3 fatty acids are a category of polyunsaturated fats present in sources like fish oil and other dietary options. They are known for their anti-inflammatory and antioxidant characteristics, as well as their ability to enhance lipid profiles and endothelial function. In cancer patients undergoing anthracycline chemotherapy, omega-3 fatty acids have been shown to have a protective effect against AIC⁵⁴. They reduce the incidence and severity of left ventricular dysfunction, as well as the risk of heart failure and mortality⁵⁵. A meta-analysis of RCTs showed that omega-3 fatty acids significantly reduced the risk of developing cardiac dysfunction in patients treated with anthracyclines compared to controls⁵⁶.

6. Conclusion

Anthracycline-induced cardiotoxicity is a serious complication of anthracycline chemotherapy that can lead to irreversible damage to the myocardium and subsequent morbidity and mortality in cancer patients. The exact molecular mechanism of AIC remains controversial and is likely to be multifactorial, but the generation of ROS and subsequent oxidative stress is the primary cause of AIC. Extensive efforts have been conducted regarding monitoring, prevention, and treatment of AIC, ranging from the continuous infusion of anthracycline, the use of liposomal drugs or their less cardiotoxic derivative, and concomitant therapy by cardioprotective agents. Evidence suggests that prophylactic treatment with cardioprotective agents is the best way to prevent AIC in high-risk patients. Dexrazoxane, beta-blockers, ACEIs and ARBs, statins, and omega-3 fatty acids are among the cardioprotective agents that have been shown to have a protective effect against

AIC in cancer patients undergoing anthracycline chemotherapy. However, further studies are required to identify the most effective and safe strategies for preventing and treating AIC in cancer patients.

Declarations

Competing interests

The authors report no conflicts of interest.

Authors' contribution

All authors were involved in data collection, design of the article, interpretation of results, review, and manuscript preparation.

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Ethical considerations

The authors have checked the article for plagiarism, data fabrication, double publication, and redundancy.

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References

- Cardinale D, Bacchiani G, Beggiano M, Colombo A, and Cipolla CM. Strategies to prevent and treat cardiovascular risk in cancer patients. *Semin Oncol*. 2013; 40(2):186-198. DOI: [10.1053/j.seminoncol.2013.01.008](https://doi.org/10.1053/j.seminoncol.2013.01.008)
- Ky B, Vejpongsa P, Yeh ET, Force T, and Moslehi JJ. Emerging paradigms in cardiomyopathies associated with cancer therapies. *Circ Res*. 2013; 113(6): 754-764. DOI: [10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.113.300218](https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.113.300218)
- Eschenhagen T, Force T, Ewer MS, de Keulenaer GW, Suter TM, Anker SD, et al. Cardiovascular side effects of cancer therapies: A position statement from the Heart Failure Association of the European Society of Cardiology. *Eur J Heart Fail*. 2011; 13(1): 1-10. DOI: [10.1093/eurjhf/hfq213](https://doi.org/10.1093/eurjhf/hfq213)
- Smith LA, Cornelius VR, Plummer CJ, Levitt G, Verrill M, Canney P, et al. Cardiotoxicity of anthracycline agents for the treatment of cancer: Systematic review and meta-analysis of randomised controlled trials. *BMC Cancer*. 2010; 10: 337. DOI: [10.1186/1471-2407-10-337](https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2407-10-337)
- Cardinale D, Colombo A, Lamantia G, Colombo N, Civelli M, De Giacomi G, et al. Anthracycline-induced cardiomyopathy: Clinical relevance and response to pharmacologic therapy. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2010; 55(3): 213-220. DOI: [10.1016/j.jacc.2009.03.095](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacc.2009.03.095)
- Gewirtz DA. A critical evaluation of the mechanisms of action proposed for the antitumor effects of the anthracycline antibiotics adriamycin and daunorubicin. *Biochem Pharmacol*. 1999; 57(7): 727-741. DOI: [10.1016/S0006-2952\(98\)00307-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-2952(98)00307-4)
- Force T, and Wang Y. Mechanism-based engineering against anthracycline cardiotoxicity. *Circulation*. 2013; 128(2): 98-100. DOI:

- [10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.113.003688](https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.113.003688)
8. Kocik M, Zimovjanova M, Petruzelka L, Kodydkova J, Vavrova L, and Zak A. Oxidative stress after anthracycline therapy in patients with solid tumors. *Cas Lek Ces.* 2012; 151(10): 463-467. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/23256630/>
 9. Chung WB, Yi JE, Jin JY, Choi YS, Park CS, Park WC, et al. Early cardiac function monitoring for detection of subclinical Doxorubicin cardiotoxicity in young adult patients with breast cancer. *J Breast Cancer.* 2013; 16(2): 178-183. DOI: [10.4048/jbc.2013.16.2.178](https://doi.org/10.4048/jbc.2013.16.2.178)
 10. Vejpongsa P, and Yeh ET. Prevention of anthracycline-induced cardiotoxicity: Challenges and opportunities. *J Am Coll Cardiol.* 2014; 64(9): 938-945. DOI: [10.1016/j.jacc.2014.06.1167](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacc.2014.06.1167)
 11. Unverferth DV, Magorien RD, Unverferth BP, Talley RL, Balcerzak SP, and Baba N. Human myocardial morphologic and functional changes in the first 24 hours after doxorubicin administration. *Cancer Treat Rep.* 1981; 65(11-12): 1093-1097. PubMed PMID: 7296554
 12. Geisberg CA, and Sawyer DB. Mechanisms of anthracycline cardiotoxicity and strategies to decrease cardiac damage. *Curr Hypertens Rep.* 2010; 12(6): 404-410. DOI: [10.1007/s11906-010-0146-y](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11906-010-0146-y)
 13. Horenstein MS, Vander Heide RS, and L'Ecuyer TJ. Molecular basis of anthracycline-induced cardiotoxicity and its prevention. *Mol Genet Metab.* 2000; 71(1-2): 436-44. DOI: [10.1006/mgme.2000.3043](https://doi.org/10.1006/mgme.2000.3043)
 14. Tokarska-Schlattner M, Zaugg M, Zuppinger C, Wallimann T, and Schlattner U. New insights into doxorubicin-induced cardiotoxicity: The critical role of cellular energetics. *J Mol Cell Cardiol.* 2006; 41(3): 389-405. DOI: [10.1016/j.yjmcc.2006.06.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yjmcc.2006.06.009)
 15. Wang L, Ma W, Markovich R, Chen JW, and Wang PH. Regulation of cardiomyocyte apoptotic signaling by insulin-like growth factor I. *Circ Res.* 1998; 83(5): 516-522. DOI: [10.1161/01.RES.83.5.516](https://doi.org/10.1161/01.RES.83.5.516)
 16. Childs AC, Phaneuf SL, Dirks AJ, Phillips T, and Leeuwenburgh C. Doxorubicin treatment *in vivo* causes cytochrome C release and cardiomyocyte apoptosis, as well as increased mitochondrial efficiency, superoxide dismutase activity, and Bcl-2: Bax ratio. *Cancer Res.* 2002; 62(16): 4592-4598.
 17. Volkova M, Russell R 3rd. Anthracycline cardiotoxicity: Prevalence, pathogenesis and treatment. *Curr Cardiol Rev.* 2011; 7(4): 214-220. DOI: [10.2174/157340311799960645](https://doi.org/10.2174/157340311799960645)
 18. Minotti G, Menna P, Salvatorelli E, Cairo G, and Gianni L. Anthracyclines: Molecular advances and pharmacologic developments in antitumor activity and cardiotoxicity. *Pharmacol Rev.* 2004; 56(2): 185-229. DOI: [10.1124/pr.56.2.6](https://doi.org/10.1124/pr.56.2.6)
 19. Liu J, Mao W, Ding B, and Liang CS. ERKs/p53 signal transduction pathway is involved in doxorubicin-induced apoptosis in H9c2 cells and cardiomyocytes. *Am J Physiol Heart Circ Physiol.* 2008; 295(5): H1956-H1965. DOI: [10.1152/ajpheart.00407.2008](https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpheart.00407.2008)
 20. Tewey KM, Rowe TC, Yang L, Halligan BD, and Liu LF. Adriamycin-induced DNA damage mediated by mammalian DNA topoisomerase II. *Science.* 1984; 226(4673): 466-468. DOI: [10.1126/science.6093249](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.6093249)
 21. Vejpongsa P, and Yeh ET. Topoisomerase 2beta: A promising molecular target for primary prevention of anthracycline-induced cardiotoxicity. *Clin Pharmacol Ther.* 2014; 95(1): 45-52. DOI: [10.1038/clpt.2013.201](https://doi.org/10.1038/clpt.2013.201)
 22. Kersting G, Tzvetkov MV, Huse K, Kulle B, Hafner V, Brockmoller J, et al. Topoisomerase II beta expression level correlates with doxorubicin-induced apoptosis in peripheral blood cells. *Naunyn Schmiedebergs Arch Pharmacol.* 2006; 374(1): 21-30. DOI: [10.1007/s00210-006-0091-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00210-006-0091-0)
 23. Zhang S, Liu X, Bawa-Khalife T, Lu LS, Lyu YL, Liu LF, et al. Identification of the molecular basis of doxorubicin-induced cardiotoxicity. *Nat Med.* 2012; 18(11): 1639-1642. DOI: [10.1038/nm.2919](https://doi.org/10.1038/nm.2919)
 24. Buzdar AU, Marcus C, Smith TL, and Blumenschein GR. Early and delayed clinical cardiotoxicity of doxorubicin. *Cancer.* 1985; 55(12): 2761-2765. DOI: [10.1002/1097-0142\(19850615\)55:12%3C2761::AID-CNCR2820551206%3E3.0.CO;2-P](https://doi.org/10.1002/1097-0142(19850615)55:12%3C2761::AID-CNCR2820551206%3E3.0.CO;2-P)
 25. Yeh ET, and Bickford CL. Cardiovascular complications of cancer therapy: Incidence, pathogenesis, diagnosis, and management. *J Am Coll Cardiol.* 2009; 53(24): 2231-2247. DOI: [10.1016/j.jacc.2009.02.050](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacc.2009.02.050)
 26. Abu-Khalaf MM, Juneja V, Chung GG, DiGiovanna MP, Sipples R, McGurk M, et al. Long-term assessment of cardiac function after dose-dense and -intense sequential doxorubicin (A), paclitaxel (T), and cyclophosphamide (C) as adjuvant therapy for high risk breast cancer. *Breast Cancer Res Treat.* 2007; 104(3): 341-349. DOI: [10.1007/s10549-006-9413-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10549-006-9413-7)
 27. Von Hoff DD, Layard MW, Basa P, Davis HL Jr, Von Hoff AL, Rozencweig M, et al. Risk factors for doxorubicin-induced congestive heart failure. *Ann Intern Med.* 1979; 91(5): 710-717. DOI: [10.7326/0003-4819-91-5-710](https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-91-5-710)
 28. Visscher H, Ross CJ, Rassekh SR, Barhdadi A, Dube MP, Al-Saloos H, et al. Pharmacogenomic prediction of anthracycline-induced cardiotoxicity in children. *J Clin Oncol.* 2012; 30(13): 1422-1428. DOI: [10.1200/JCO.2010.34.3467](https://doi.org/10.1200/JCO.2010.34.3467)
 29. Hertz DL, Caram MV, Kidwell KM, Thibert JN, Gersch C, Seewald NJ, et al. Evidence for association of SNPs in ABCB1 and CBR3, but not RAC2, NCF4, SLC28A3 or TOP2B, with chronic cardiotoxicity in a cohort of breast cancer patients treated with anthracyclines. *Pharmacogenomics.* 2016; 17(3): 231-240. DOI: [10.2217/pgs.15.162](https://doi.org/10.2217/pgs.15.162)
 30. Visscher H, Rassekh SR, Sandor GS, Caron HN, van Dalen EC, Kremer LC, et al. Genetic variants in SLC22A17 and SLC22A7 are associated with anthracycline-induced cardiotoxicity in children. *Pharmacogenomics.* 2015; 16(10): 1065-1076. DOI: [10.2217/pgs.15.61](https://doi.org/10.2217/pgs.15.61)
 31. Reichwagen A, Ziepert M, Kreuz M, Godtel-Armbrust U, Rixecker T, Poeschel V, et al. Association of NADPH oxidase polymorphisms with anthracycline-induced cardiotoxicity in the RICOVER-60 trial of patients with aggressive CD20(+) B-cell lymphoma. *Pharmacogenomics.* 2015; 16(4): 361-372. DOI: [10.2217/pgs.14.179](https://doi.org/10.2217/pgs.14.179)
 32. Wang X, Sun CL, Quinones-Lombrana A, Singh P, Landier W, Hageman L, et al. CELF4 variant and anthracycline-related cardiomyopathy: A children's oncology group genome-wide association study. *J Clin Oncol.* 2016; 34(8): 863-870. DOI: [10.1200/JCO.2015.63.4550](https://doi.org/10.1200/JCO.2015.63.4550)
 33. Leong SL, Chaiyakunapruk N, and Lee SW. Candidate gene association studies of anthracycline-induced cardiotoxicity: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Sci Rep.* 2017; 7(1): 39. DOI: [10.1038/s41598-017-00075-1](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-00075-1)
 34. Storm G, van Hoesel QG, de Groot G, Kop W, Steerenberg PA, and Hillen FC. A comparative study on the antitumor effect, cardiotoxicity and nephrotoxicity of doxorubicin given as a bolus, continuous infusion or entrapped in liposomes in the Lou/M Wsl rat. *Cancer Chemother Pharmacol.* 1989; 24(6): 341-8. DOI: [10.1007/BF00257439](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00257439)
 35. Legha SS, Benjamin RS, Mackay B, Ewer M, Wallace S, Valdivieso M, et al. Reduction of doxorubicin cardiotoxicity by prolonged continuous intravenous infusion. *Ann Intern Med.* 1982; 96(2): 133-139. DOI: [10.7326/0003-4819-96-2-133](https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-96-2-133)
 36. Waterhouse DN, Tardi PG, Mayer LD, and Bally MB. A comparison of liposomal formulations of doxorubicin with drug administered in free form: Changing toxicity profiles. *Drug Saf.* 2001; 24(12): 903-920. DOI: [10.2165/00002018-200124120-00004](https://doi.org/10.2165/00002018-200124120-00004)
 37. Sawaya H, Sebag IA, Plana JC, Januzzi JL, Ky B, Cohen V, et al. Early detection and prediction of cardiotoxicity in chemotherapy-treated patients. *Am J Card.* 2011; 107(9): 1375-1380. DOI: [10.1016/j.amjcard.2011.01.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amjcard.2011.01.006)
 38. Wassmuth R, Lentzsch S, Erdbruegger U, Schulz-Menger J, Doerken B, Dietz R, et al. Subclinical cardiotoxic effects of anthracyclines as assessed by magnetic resonance imaging-a pilot study. *Am Heart J.* 2001; 141(6): 1007-1013. DOI: [10.1067/mhj.2001.115436](https://doi.org/10.1067/mhj.2001.115436)
 39. Okumura H, Iuchi K, Yoshida T, Nakamura S, Takeshima M, Takamatsu H, et al. Brain natriuretic peptide is a predictor of anthracycline-induced cardiotoxicity. *Acta Haematol.* 2000; 104(4): 158-163. DOI: [10.1159/000046508](https://doi.org/10.1159/000046508)
 40. Sandri MT, Salvatici M, Cardinale D, Zorzino L, Passerini R, Lentati P, et al. N-terminal pro-B-type natriuretic peptide after high-dose chemotherapy: a marker predictive of cardiac dysfunction?. *Clin Chem.* 2005; 51(8): 1405-1410. DOI: [10.1373/clinchem.2005.050153](https://doi.org/10.1373/clinchem.2005.050153)
 41. Swain SM, Whaley FS, and Ewer MS. Congestive heart failure in patients treated with doxorubicin: A retrospective analysis of three trials. *Cancer.* 2003; 97(11): 2869-2879. DOI: [10.1002/cncr.11407](https://doi.org/10.1002/cncr.11407)
 42. Lipshultz SE, Adams MJ, Colan SD, Constine LS, Herman EH, and Hsu DT. Long-term cardiovascular toxicity in children, adolescents, and young adults who receive cancer therapy: pathophysiology, course, monitoring, management, prevention, and research directions: A scientific statement from the American Heart Association. *Circulation.* 2013; 128(17): 1927-1995. DOI: [10.1161/CIR.0b013e3182a88099](https://doi.org/10.1161/CIR.0b013e3182a88099)
 43. Cardinale D, Colombo A, Sandri MT, et al. Prevention of high-dose chemotherapy-induced cardiotoxicity in high-risk patients by angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibition. *Circulation.* 2006;

- 114(23): 2474-2481. DOI: [10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.106.635144](https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.106.635144)
44. Swain SM, and Vici P. The current and future role of dexrazoxane as a cardioprotectant in anthracycline treatment: expert panel review. *J Cancer Res Clin Oncol*. 2004; 130(1): 1-7. DOI: [10.1007/s00432-003-0498-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00432-003-0498-7)
45. Tebbi CK, London WB, Friedman D, Villaluna D, De Alarcon PA, Constine LS, et al. Dexrazoxane-associated risk for acute myeloid leukemia/myelodysplastic syndrome and other secondary malignancies in pediatric Hodgkin's disease. *J Clin Oncol*. 2007; 25(5): 493-500. DOI: [10.1200/JCO.2005.02.3879](https://doi.org/10.1200/JCO.2005.02.3879)
46. Lyman GH, Lyman CH, and Agboola O. Risk models for predicting chemotherapy-induced neutropenia. *Oncologist*. 2005; 10(6): 427-437. DOI: [10.1634/theoncologist.10-6-427](https://doi.org/10.1634/theoncologist.10-6-427)
47. van Dalen EC, van der Pal HJ, Caron HN, and Kremer LC. Different dosage schedules for reducing cardiotoxicity in cancer patients receiving anthracycline chemotherapy. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2009; (4): CD005008. DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD005008.pub3](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD005008.pub3)
48. Wihandono A, Azhar Y, Abdurahman M, Hidayat S. The role of lisinopril and bisoprolol to prevent anthracycline induced cardiotoxicity in locally advanced breast cancer patients. *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev*. 2021; 22(9):2847. Doi: [10.31557/APJCP.2021.22.9.2847](https://doi.org/10.31557/APJCP.2021.22.9.2847)
49. Avila MS, Ayub-Ferreira SM, de Barros Wanderley MR, das Dores Cruz F, Gonçalves Brandão SM, Carvalho Rigaud VO, et al. Carvedilol for prevention of chemotherapy-related cardiotoxicity: The CECCY trial. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2018; 71(20): 2281-2290. Available at: <https://www.jacc.org/doi/abs/10.1016/j.jacc.2018.02.049>
50. Gulati G, Heck SL, Ree AH, Hoffmann P, Schulz-Menger J, Fagerland MW, et al. Prevention of cardiac dysfunction during adjuvant breast cancer therapy (PRADA): a 2x2 factorial, randomized, placebo-controlled, double-blind clinical trial of candesartan and metoprolol. *Eur Heart J*. 2016; 37(21): 1671-1680. DOI: [10.1093/eurheartj/ehw022](https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehw022)
51. Genuino AJ, Chaikledkaew U, The DO, Reungwetwattana T, Thakkinstian A. Adjuvant trastuzumab regimen for HER2-positive early-stage breast cancer: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Expert Rev Clin Pharmacol*. 2019; 12(8): 815-824. Doi: [10.1080/17512433.2019.1637252](https://doi.org/10.1080/17512433.2019.1637252)
52. Kalay N, Basar E, Ozdogru I, Er O, Cetinkaya Y, Dogan A, et al. Protective effects of carvedilol against anthracycline-induced cardiomyopathy. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2006; 48(11): 2258-2262. Available at: <https://www.jacc.org/doi/abs/10.1016/j.jacc.2006.07.052>
53. Cardinale D, Colombo A, Lamantia G, Colombo N, Civelli M, De Giacomo M, et al. Anthracycline-induced cardiomyopathy: Clinical relevance and response to pharmacologic therapy. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2010; 55(3): 213-220. Available at: <https://www.jacc.org/doi/abs/10.1016/j.jacc.2009.03.095>
54. Seicean S, Seicean A, Plana JC, Budd GT, and Marwick TH. Effect of statin therapy on the risk for incident heart failure in patients with breast cancer receiving anthracycline chemotherapy: an observational clinical cohort study. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2012; 60(23): 2384-2390. Available at: <https://www.jacc.org/doi/full/10.1016/j.jacc.2012.07.067>
55. Djoussé L, Akinkuolie AO, Wu JH, Ding EL, Gaziano JM. Fish consumption, omega-3 fatty acids and risk of heart failure: a meta-analysis. *Clinical nutrition*. 2012; 31(6):846-53. Doi: [10.1016/j.clnu.2012.05.010](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clnu.2012.05.010)
56. Shen S, Gong C, Jin K, Zhou L, Xiao Y, Ma L. Omega-3 fatty acid supplementation and coronary heart disease risks: a meta-analysis of randomized controlled clinical trials. *Frontiers in Nutrition*. 2022; 3(9):20.